

How to engage engineering students to Physics: A case report of an Introductory Physics course taught in the first year of an Engineering programme

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Abstract

Lecturers who teach Introductory Physics courses to engineering students face several challenges. Besides the usually high number of students (> 100), there is a preconception in considering the contents of physics courses very complex. These aspects, together with the fact that enrolment is required for an engineering study plan, make physics a course with low student engagement. This paper describes strategies and activities implemented in an Introductory Physics course (Physics EE), for first-year students of Industrial Electronics and Computers Engineering (Integrated Master) at the University of Minho to increase students' motivation, engagement and active learning. The implemented strategy includes: sharing the learning outcomes at the beginning of each lesson to help and guide students to successfully complete the tasks related to the topic and study more effectively; regular use of Audience Response Systems to encourage participation and give immediate feedback; use of in-class exercises to promote critical thinking and cooperation in the discussion of complex concepts; two-stage assessment (individual test followed by a similar test in groups), to promote collaborative learning and immediate feedback. These approaches took place during the 2018/2019 academic year in face-to-face teaching and in the 2019/2020 academic year in online teaching, due to the COVID-19 pandemic. In both semesters, the students' perceptions of the implemented changes were collected through anonymous questionnaires during the semester and at the end of term. The results indicate that, for both semesters, the students were satisfied with the implemented changes; they recognised the value of the immediate effective feedback to improve their learning experience and revealed high levels of satisfaction with the classes. These findings are consistent among students who attended face-to-face and online classes, and among students from different disciplinary areas, suggesting that the implementation of active learning strategies in this physics course may be transferable to different teaching contexts and scientific areas.

Keywords: Introductory Physics; Students Engagement; Active Learning; Collaborative Learning; Audience Response Systems (ARS).

1 Introduction

Teaching a specific course from a disciplinary area not directly related to the programme is challenging. Students tend to focus more on courses directly related to the area of the programme due to their higher personal affinity to these subjects. Therefore, the intrinsic motivation of students is low (Zavala et al., 2015), which leads to a lack of engagement in the activities of the course. This situation can be aggravated when a large number of students are enrolled and when the subject is regarded as complex by them. A typical example is Introductory Physics in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) programmes (Redish, 1994), many of them not directly related with Physics in terms of content. In addition, these courses are usually taught to a large number of students from different programmes.

Extensive research has demonstrated the effectiveness of active learning approaches in promoting students' engagement in STEM programmes (e.g., Freeman et al., 2014; Hake, 1998; Prince, 2004), in particular in Introductory Physics courses (Meltzer & Thornton, 2012). Such evidence makes the use of active learning activities adequate to the present case. Active learning is a broad concept that can be defined as an interactive student-centred instructional approach that encourages students to be active and engaged in their learning process by performing meaningful activities and by thinking critically about them (Bonwell & Eison, 1991, Hernández-de-Menéndez et al., 2019; Prince, 2004). The literature offers an extensive menu of active learning

activities, from short or simple activities (e.g., questions and answers) to longer and most complex ones (e.g., team-based learning), which can be performed individually (e.g., one-minute paper), in small groups (e.g., debates) or large groups (e.g., quizzes using Audience Response Systems; ARS; Hernández-de-Menéndez et al., 2019; Prince & Felder 2007). To be effective, these activities must be designed around relevant learning outcomes that express the understanding of the important knowledge and skills to be learned (Prince, 2004) and feedback and support must be provided throughout the process (Yadav et al., 2011).

The benefits of active learning are well documented in the literature, with several studies showing its positive relationship with students' motivation, satisfaction, lecture attendance, engagement with learning (Deslauriers et al., 2019; Hernández-de-Menéndez et al., 2019; Prince, 2004), and with the acquisition of essential skills such as teamwork, communication, autonomy, responsibility, self-regulation, critical thinking and problem-solving (Hernández-de-Menéndez et al., 2019; Prince, 2004). The latter constitute higher-order thinking skills (HOTS), which are particularly relevant in engineering education (Asok et al., 2016; Hernández-de-Menéndez et al., 2019). Research also found evidence that active learning improves students' overall academic performance in STEM courses compared to traditional lecturing, in particular students developed a better understanding of abstract physics concepts (Freeman et al., 2014), scored higher in conceptual inventory tests (Deslauriers et al., 2019; Hake, 1998) and were less likely to fail (Freeman et al., 2014).

Despite all the evidence of success, many students still consider the lecturing classes more effective and prefer to stay in their comfort zone, resisting being actively engaged in their learning process (Deslauriers et al., 2019). Therefore, to enhance the success of active learning, both parties must understand its nature, experience its value and accept that active learning leads to deeper learning. Teachers play an important role in promoting active learning, explaining this learning approach to students, engaging them in relevant activities and sharing timely feedback that maximizes their learning potential.

Based on these principles, the present case describes active learning strategies and activities implemented in an Introductory Physics course for first-year students of Industrial Electronics and Computers Engineering (Integrated Master) at the University of Minho, to increase their motivation, engagement, and active learning. It also reports the students' perceptions of their learning experience. The paper is organised as follows: after a brief description of the course, details of the implemented approaches are presented, followed by the description of the methods used to collect student perceptions. Then, the obtained results are analysed, and discussed and the general conclusions of this case study are presented.

2 Case Report Context

The reported approaches took place during the 2018/2019 academic year in face-to-face teaching and in the 2019/2020 academic year in online teaching due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

2.1 Course Description

The Curricular Unit (CU), Physics EE, required for all the students enrolled in the Integrated Masters in Engineering, covers the fields of Mechanics and Waves. The CU is organised in lecture, or theoretical, classes (2 h/week), taught simultaneously for all the students, and theory-practice classes (2h/week), where the students are divided into classes of 35-40 students each. The CU is taught in the second semester of the integrated master for 15 weeks, and attendance is not mandatory. In 2018/2019, approximately 67 % of the students were enrolled in the CU for the first time and in 2019/2020, the value was approximately 63 %. The remaining students did not have success in the previous academic year. The number of students and the distribution according to gender is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Distribution of the students enrolled in the curricular unit Physics EE by the academic years under study and by sex.

Academic year	Nº of students	Female	Male
2018/2019	126	18 (14.3 %)	108 (85.7 %)
2019/2020	132	16 (12.1 %)	116 (87.9 %)

3 Implemented Approaches

The first day of class is intended to be one of the most important classes of all the semester (Davis, 2009) since it is the moment when the students know the teacher, discuss the teaching and learning approaches, the evaluation criteria and create expectations about the course. How the semester will run in terms of teaching, learning and the relationship teacher-student will largely depend on this first moment. It is also important for the teacher to know the expectations of their students towards the CU, before starting the classes, especially in a course with so many students, where it is almost impossible to have a conversation with every single student. To overcome this problem, students enrolled in the CU were invited, one week before the first class, to answer an anonymous questionnaire about their expectations towards the CU. The analysis of the questionnaire gave important tips on the students' expectations, helping to design the first day of classes and to present the strategies and active learning activities that would be implemented throughout the semester.

It is also important that students be aware, in advance, of the proposals for the assessment, the teaching and learning methodologies, and be actively involved in their analysis, discussion and adjustment, if necessary. For this reason, one week before the beginning of the semester, the teacher shared with students in the e-learning platform available at the University of Minho, detailed information about the assessment proposals, the methodologies to be adopted in class, and a plan of all teaching and assessment activities.

The theoretical lessons of 2018/2019 were taught using PowerPoints and, whenever possible, some experimental demonstrations with homemade resources were used as well as interactive simulations available on the internet. At the beginning of each class, students received explicit information about the sessions' learning outcomes, to clarify the purpose of the activities to be performed and their relation to the knowledge and skills to be learned. Students' understanding of the learning outcomes and their connection to the learning activities is essential to encourage their engagement and guide them during tasks (Prince, 2004).

Throughout classes, active learning strategies were implemented to increase students' interest, motivation, and commitment in classes and to promote their active learning attitude and practice. The traditional lecturing activity was reduced, and multiple active learning activities were interspersed in classes, such as ARS, think-pair-share, in-class exercises and two-stage assessment.

Audience Response Systems were used regularly during the semester to encourage students' participation and engagement in classes and to obtain and give immediate feedback (Gousseau et al. 2016). Students could use their smartphones to anonymously answer multiple types of questions (memory, conceptual, application, open-ended), combining different degrees of complexity. One of the advantages of these systems is that they allow the teacher to adapt, in real-time, the pedagogical strategies and activities.

Students were engaged in debates and "think-pair-share" activities to evaluate their level of understanding of the content, to promote critical thinking, and to obtain and give immediate feedback. At the end of each lesson, questions were used to assess the student's understanding of the key concept(s) or to identify misconceptions to be clarified at that moment, or eventually, in the next class.

In-class exercises were employed in theory-practice classes and in some lecturing classes when appropriate to focus student's attention on interpretation and analysis, to promote critical thinking and cooperation in the discussion of complex concepts, and to co-create solutions. Students worked in informal groups, and during the group discussion, they were asked to explain to the class their qualitative reasoning. When misconceptions were identified by the teacher in a given group, they were addressed to the whole class. In this way, the dialogue between student-student and student-teacher was promoted as well as the student's engagement towards the course.

A two-stage assessment was applied in this course for the first time in the academic year of 2018/2019 to promote collaborative learning and to obtain and give immediate feedback. In the two-stage assessment, students firstly completed an individual test for 70 minutes. Afterwards, in groups of 3 or 4 students, previously organised by the students themselves, they solved a group test for 40 minutes. The individual test was

composed of multiple-choice questions, requiring justification of the chosen options and of the application problems. The group test had questions similar to those of the individual test. Students had to reach a consensus on their answer since only a single test-answer sheet was delivered to the group. The two-stage tests transformed the assessment moment into a learning experience, promoted collaborative work and peer instruction, and offered immediate feedback as a result of the discussion with pairs. It also contributed to increasing students' motivation and engagement over the semester, as reported by others (Rieger & Heine, 2014). In determining the final test grade for each student, a weighting of 85% and 15% for the individual and the group test respectively was used. Students were previously informed that if the group score was lower than the individual test grade, the group test score would be excluded in calculating the final test grade.

During the academic year 2019/2020, due to the suspension of face-to-face classes, the course was delivered online, combining synchronous and asynchronous modes, therefore some changes were implemented relative to the approach of the previous academic year. One week before each synchronous session, all the support materials for the session, comprising annotated PowerPoints with voice narration, challenging problems, to encourage the debate during online class, and pre-readings indications notes, were disseminated through the e-learning platform. With this kind of "flipped classroom", the synchronous session was converted into an open discussion, where students could ask questions to clarify their doubts. In these sessions, the use of ARS was done in the same way as in face-to-face classes.

The assessment method was also changed since it was not possible to have physical working groups and the two-stage assessment was not suitable for an online environment. Considering the importance of collaborative learning and team working, the elaboration of a small project in groups of 4 students was proposed, using the Padlet platform, and also an individual online test at the end of the semester. The project, equal for all the groups, was related to the physical concepts underlying the operation of the Bom Jesus do Monte funicular (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bom_Jesus_do_Monte_Funicular).

4 Methods

Evidence of students' expectations and perceptions was collected, in both academic years, throughout and at the end of the semester, using anonymous questionnaires that included both quantitative and qualitative data to obtain the broadest picture of students' reactions. The questionnaire about their expectations towards the CU included three dimensions: (i) Perceptions about the demand and importance of the CU; (ii) Students' attitudes towards classes; (iii) Use of mobile phones in teaching activities. Students' perceptions of the two stage-assessment were collected, during the academic year 2018/2019, after the first assessment, through a questionnaire that included four open-ended questions about the positive and negative aspects of this type of evaluation; recommendations to the colleagues who chose to solve only the individual test; and other free comments/suggestions about this type of assessment. To assess the students' perceptions and satisfaction with the applied methodologies and the pedagogical dimension of the use of ARS, students were invited to answer an anonymous questionnaire at the end of each semester. Closed questions with statements were used and the students rated them according to their degree of agreement, using a 7-point Likert scale (1- Strongly Disagree; 7 - Strongly Agree). At the end of the questionnaire, the students were asked to express their opinions regarding the most positive aspects of the performed activities and suggestions for improvement. Informal conversations with students during or after lessons were also important to determine whether the implemented approaches were working. The results were used to make adjustments in the pedagogical strategy and activities throughout the semester.

5 Students' Perceptions

5.1 Expectation toward the curricular unit

Around 64% and 45% of the students enrolled in the CU in the academic years of 2018/2019 and 2019/2020, respectively, answered a first questionnaire about their expectations towards the CU. For both academic years, the great majority of the students (around 70%) considered the CU to be demanding, but they also recognised

the importance of the CU for their course. Regarding their attitudes towards the classes, although the presence was not mandatory, around 68% of the students considered class attendance as an obligation, in the sense that they feel that they need to attend the classes, but only 30% used to have an active participation during classes.

5.2 Two stage-assessment

Eighty-nine out of the 106 students that attended the first test have done a two stage-assessment, and 46 (52%) students have answered the questionnaire. All students, except two, recommend the two stage-assessment. Concerning the positive aspects, most students referred to the collaborative work provided during the test and the immediate feedback obtained from the interaction with their group mates that emerged during the second stage of the assessment. Besides this, it was interesting to note some other quotes:

"Similarity with the individual test and equivalent degree of difficulty." (student A)

"I met new people. I didn't know the students in my group." (student B)

"The second opportunity to solve problems already proposed individually, now with higher coolness and conscience." (student C)

As a less positive aspect, most of the students indicated the duration of the second part of the test since the time was limited to discuss and reach a consensus on the answers. Increasing the time for the group test was the main recommendation given in the qualitative responses.

5.3 Use of audience response systems

A total of 44 (34,9%) students in 2018/2019 and 80 (60,6%) students in 2019/2020 returned the questionnaire. In Figure 1, the average value obtained is compared for the following statements:

- Statement 1 – "It allowed me to have immediate feedback."
- Statement 2 - "My participation in these classes/sessions has improved."
- Statement 3 - "It facilitated my learning."
- Statement 4 - "It prepared me better for the assessment."
- Statement 5 - "It allowed me to better assess whether I understood the subjects."

Figure 1. Comparison of average results for ARS statements.

Also interesting were the most mentioned positive aspects in the open-ended questions of the questionnaire, list in table 2.

Table 2. Comparison of students' feedback on the use of ARS in open-ended questions.

Positive Aspects	2018/2019	2019/2020
Understanding/consolidation of course contents	25.0%	27.5%
Improves/increases student-teacher interactivity	28.0%	25.0%

These results clearly indicate the good acceptance of ARS by the students, which correlates with their opinions regarding improvements. In fact, the great majority of students pointed out "*nothing to change*" and few students mentioned: "*increase the response time*" and also "*trying to control the noise during discussion*".

5.4 Students' final comments on the implemented approaches

Most of the students were satisfied with the implemented strategies and activities. Among the positive comments collected in the anonymous questionnaire distributed by the teacher, students have highlighted the students-teacher interaction, the learning environment, the teamwork and the variety of learning tasks. They also mentioned that the course was well structured and organised. In response to the anonymous CU survey, implemented at the end of each semester by the University of Minho's Internal System of Quality Assurance, students commented that they enjoyed the course and the implemented approaches, and highlighted the two-stage assessment and the ARS activities. Students have also identified some aspects to be improved, most of them related to the increase in time for the completion of some tasks.

6 Discussion

According to the results of the student's expectations toward the CU, specifically regarding the low percentage of active participation in classes (30%), it is important to explain the value of the proposed activities for the classes, and establish expectations for students' engagement and reinforce them throughout the term. It is also important to communicate, focus on the learning outcomes and what students will be able to achieve at the end of the course.

The students' perceptions about the implemented approaches in this CU in both academic years are positive, in general. The feedback and the collaborative work, as well as the deeper understanding achieved during the group discussion in the two-stage assessment, were the most important gains referred by the students, which are in line with the literature (Gilley & Clarkston 2014; Wieman et al. 2014). Even if the duration of the group test was one of the negative aspects reported by the students, they felt more motivated and less stressed. It was found that the final group score was equal to or better than the individual score for almost all the students. This was also one of the aspects that contributed to the students' motivation and engagement towards the CU.

According to Hassanin et al. (2016), the use of ARS, in an anonymous way, removes any inhibitions or embarrassment, allowing the students to become active participants during classes and increase their engagement and learning. It also provided the teacher real-time information about the achievement of learning outcomes planned for the lesson, allowing, if necessary, adjustments to the lesson plan. The results indicated that the students, in face-to-face and online classes, had positive perceptions of the use of ARS as reported in the literature (Christianson, 2020). In addition, most of the students reported that the technology improved the students-teacher interactivity and helped them understand course subjects.

The analysis of students' perceptions was based on data collected from self-reported surveys, relying on their ability to adequately self-report the lived experience. However, self-report is subject to biases that may affect the validity of the results (Podsakoff et al., 2003). The combination of observation with methods of collecting

quantitative and qualitative data will allow obtaining in-depth information from multiple sources and increase the understanding of the students' experiences.

The continuation of the application of active learning strategies and activities to the Introductory Physics course suggests the development of metrics to systematically measure active learning results in students' satisfaction and engagement and academic performance (e.g., conceptual inventory tests; final grades, pass rates).

7 Conclusion

This study reports the use of active learning strategies and activities to increase students' engagement and motivation in a large Introductory Physics course for engineering students. This study also presents some results of students' perceptions towards the implemented approaches during the 2018/2019 academic year in face-to-face teaching and the 2019/2020 academic year in online teaching. The strategies and activities proved to be adequate, regardless of the type of the lessons, to achieve important goals in the learning process: motivation, participation and engagement of students in a course with a high number of students (>100), often perceived as difficult and demanding. Interestingly, the students' perceptions and comments about the experience, namely in ARS (Figure 1), were similar in both analysed academic years (the pre-lockdown 2018/2019 and during the lockdown in 2019/2020), suggesting that active learning strategies are beneficial for learning both in face-to-face and online teaching.

Students who are accustomed to traditional lectures may need time to adjust to active learning methodologies. The same applies to teachers, the planning and the preparation for these strategies need considerable dedication at first. However, once getting familiar with the approaches and technologies, activities become less time demanding without losing the strength in engaging and challenging students so that they experience meaningful learning.

8 References

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